

5. Laboratory scale cultivation tests for nutrient saturated membranes

The aim of the experiments performed by BZN was to assess the efficiency of the nutrient-saturated membranes as a possible fertiliser by laboratory-scale cultivation tests based on nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content of the soil and plant tissues.

5.1 Materials and methods

Sandy soil with low nutrient content was filled into 7x7 cm pots till 2 cm from the top. 2x2 cm pieces were cut out from the control (unsaturated), phosphorus (NaH_2PO_4) saturated and nitrogen + potassium (KNO_3) saturated membranes that were prepared and provided by VTT. Each of these pieces was cut into thin slices (Figure 11. A). The slices were spread on the surface of the pots (Figure 11.B), then covered with an additional layer of soil (approx. 2 cm), and two holes were made with a conical centrifuge tube. Green coral lettuce 'Lollo Bionda' (*Lactuca sativa var. crispa*) seeds were sown into the holes (one seed in each hole, two seeds per pot) (Figure 11.C).

A. Cutting the membrane pieces

B. Membrane pieces spread on the soil surface

C. Lettuce seeds sown into the holes

Figure 11. Preparation of the plant experiments

Eight pots were set for each type of membrane (unsaturated, P-saturated, N+K-saturated, marked by MC, P, NK, respectively) and additional eight pots for control samples without membrane (marked by C). Pots were watered regularly and placed under artificial lights switched on from 8 AM to 6 PM. Germination of seeds was followed daily by recording the number of leaves. This cultivation test was repeated three times.

The nutrient content of the soil and plant leaves was determined at the end of the experiment. The extraction of soil and plant samples was made according to the methodology developed by Miles et al. (1983). The total nitrogen and phosphorus content of the extracts was measured by colorimetric determination of nitrate by

nitration of salicylic acid (Cataldo et al. 1975) and the vanadomolybdo-phosphoric acid colourimetric method (APHA, 2005), respectively. The potassium content of samples was measured by a HORIBA LAQUAtwin Compact Water Quality Meter.

5.2 Results

The experimental plots containing untreated membrane (MC), phosphorus-containing membrane (P), nitrogen and potassium-containing membrane (NK) and no membrane (C) were compared, based on seed germination, plant development and nutrient (N, P, K) measurements from soils and plant leaves.

Germination occurred simultaneously in all experimental settings. The number of germinated seeds in the plots containing different membranes followed the same kinetics and did not differ significantly during all three experiments.

The average number of leaves generally followed the same kinetics in the plots containing different membranes in all three experiments. There were some occasions when significant differences could be observed (e.g. on day 5 of the first experiment, the C group had a significantly lower average leaf number than the P and NK groups, and on day 29 of the third experiment, the C group had significantly lower average leaf number than the NK group), but this difference existed for one day only, and did not follow any trend. Figure 12 shows the results of the first experiment for both germination and the number of leaves.

Figure 12. Number of germinated seeds and average leaf number in the first experiment (C: no membrane, MC: unsaturated membrane, P: P-saturated membrane, NK: N+K-saturated membrane)

The nutrient content of the soil amended with membranes was not higher compared with the control group containing no membrane (Figure 13.). The nutrient content was similar in all groups in most cases. There was no significant difference in the nutrient content of the plant leaves either among the different groups (Figure 14.).

Based on the experiments described above, nutrient saturated membranes were not capable of significantly increasing the nutrient content of the soil or the plants. The addition of membranes did not affect the germination and development of plants. It should be noted that the amount of nutrients adsorbed to the cationic nanocellulose membrane was low (111 mg/m², 219 mg/m², and 459 mg/m² for N, P, K, respectively, according to the results of VTT), and these amounts cannot be expected to have a significant effect on the parameters investigated. The membrane is still under development at VTT, and partners are planning further cultivation tests with the newly developed version having a higher adsorption capacity.

Figure 13. Nutrient content of soil in the second experiment (C: no membrane, MC: unsaturated membrane, P: P-saturated membrane, NK: N+K-saturated membrane)

Figure 14. Nutrient content of leaves in the second experiment (C: no membrane, MC: unsaturated membrane, P: P-saturated membrane, NK: N+K-saturated membrane)